

THE EFFECT OF PROBLEM-BASED LEARNING ON TEACHING QUALITY IN BIOLOGY EDUCATION

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Abstract. *In the modern education system, the application of learner-centered approaches plays an important role in improving the quality of instruction. In this regard, the problem-based learning (PBL) model creates conditions for the development of learners' critical thinking, problem-solving, and independent learning skills in the teaching of biology. This article investigates the impact of implementing the problem-based learning model in biology classes on the quality of instruction. The research results show that this model increases learners' motivation, ensures their active participation in lessons, and contributes to more sustainable knowledge acquisition.*

Keywords: *problem-based learning, biology teaching, quality of instruction, active learning, critical thinking*

Introduction

Education plays an important role in the formation of an individual. It governs important processes such as shaping one's worldview, understanding the surrounding environment, observing events, reasoning, making decisions, and drawing conclusions. If we look at the history of the teaching and education system, we can see that this process has always had a developmental character. It can be noted that its development has been closely related to the progress of civilizations. If we go back a hundred years, writing, reading, completing assignments, the teaching process, and assessment were considered fully important and acceptable. During those periods, literacy was measured by these criteria. In the teaching and learning process, the teacher or instructor played a very important role, and the process was called teacher-centered or traditional teaching. Punishment in the teaching process was also considered acceptable at that time.

When we return to the present day after a hundred years, the picture of the world has changed. Rapid technological development, robotics, and internet resources have created the necessity to change the style of classrooms. Literacy is no longer limited to reading and writing skills but has been replaced by processes such as innovation, self-development, and self-learning. While learners 25 years ago received information about a subject only from school textbooks and teachers, today's learners have many opportunities and wide access to information. Learners now have sufficient materials on any topic of interest. Therefore, there has been a need to change teaching methods, classroom environments, and the education system as a whole. The changes occurring in the education system have required teachers to learn, create, and apply new pedagogical approaches. The teacher is no longer merely a provider of ready-made materials but a guide who shows the way to access these materials.

The modern education system is learner- and student-centered. Individual approach comes to the forefront, and the learner's psychology and learning pace are taken as a basis. Modern education prioritizes the application of interactive methods. One of these methods is the problem-based learning model. In modern didactics, problem-based learning (Problem-Based Learning – PBL) is considered an effective tool for developing students' critical and creative thinking. The PBL approach shapes learners not simply as recipients of information but as active participants who solve problems and apply knowledge in practice.

In the teaching of botany, this method ensures a comprehensive study of natural phenomena and the plant world. For example, when problem-based learning is applied to the topic "The impact of climate change on local flora species," learners first identify the current problems related to the topic, then investigate possible solutions, and discuss the results in the classroom. This approach

contributes to the development of both biological knowledge and scientific research skills. At this stage, learners not only acquire theoretical knowledge but also analyze information, compare it, and present their conclusions scientifically [4, p. 51].

Materials and Methods

During the research, methods such as the analysis of pedagogical literature, observation, and comparative analysis were used. During the implementation of the problem-based learning model in biology classes, changes in learners' interest in the lesson, their activity, and their level of knowledge were examined. Within the framework of the study, tasks based on real-life problems were prepared during lessons, and learners worked in groups to investigate possible solutions to the problem and present their results.

Results and Discussion

Based on the observations conducted during the teaching process, the implementation of the problem-based learning model led to the following positive outcomes:

- Learners' interest and motivation in the lesson increased.
- Critical and analytical thinking skills improved.
- Group work and communication skills were strengthened.
- The level of knowledge application increased.
- Learners' independent learning skills were developed.

This model enables students to become active participants rather than passive listeners. In subjects such as biology, which are based on experimentation and observation, problem-based learning yields more effective results. The obtained results are also consistent with the views of other researchers and indicate that the problem-based learning model is an effective tool for improving the quality of instruction.

Conclusion

The problem-based learning model plays an important role in improving the quality of instruction in biology classes. In addition to increasing students' activity, this model develops their independent thinking and problem-solving skills. Based on the research findings, the wider application of the problem-based learning model in biology classes is considered appropriate.

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